

THE ROLE OF ENGLISH LITERACY IN STUDENTS' SPIRITUAL REFLECTION

Jumaeva Sanobar Absaatovna,

Associate Professor of the Department of General Pedagogy, PhD Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami

Kholmuminova Sarviniso Jahongir kizi

English teacher of polytechnic school No. 3 Yakkabog district, Kashkadarya region

Abstract. This article examines issues related to the use of gaming technologies in English lessons in the process of educating a developed spiritual and moral personality. The concept of "role-playing game", its functions and relationship with the education and training of schoolchildren in accordance with the requirements of modern educational standards were considered. In addition, a brief classification of games that can be used in teaching schoolchildren a foreign language is proposed.

Keywords: motivation, spiritual and moral education, gaming technologies, project activities, teaching English to schoolchildren.

INTRODUCTION

Today, a new stage of development of society has begun. It is connected with the change of the mentality of society and value orientations of the younger generation. Humanity has begun to ignore such manifestation of morality as empathy, compassion, sympathy. Unfortunately, respect for others is fading into the background. Therefore, there is an acute need to educate a spiritually and morally developed personality, who is capable of not only consuming, but also giving in return.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Obviously, in order to become a full-fledged and cultured personality, students should learn the spiritual and moral values accumulated by their ancestors over many millennia. Society, entering the global cultural space, must know and successfully apply in practice the means of intercultural communication. Based on the above, we can conclude that knowledge of foreign languages plays a huge role for participants in the international space. Language is a repository of the culture of the people. It presents the historical experience of the ethnic group, aesthetic, ethical, moral and educational ideals [1]. Therefore, spiritual and moral education is actively formed in foreign language lessons, where critical thinking skills are laid, helping to compare their own beliefs with the components of social morality, generally accepted moral standards. In foreign language lessons, the teacher forms the student's worldview, since this academic discipline, in addition to linguistic competencies, concerns the problems of student behavior in a particular everyday situation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In English lessons, the problems of tolerance, charity, materialism and national culture are discussed, conversations are held about family values, strong-willed qualities, conscience, and fortitude [2]. Thus, in the process of dialogue, it is possible to achieve the objectives set in the lesson. It can be concluded that communicative learning educates and forms diligence, perseverance, activity, independence; develops imagination, thinking and memory. Reading is one of the many ways of teaching and education, as an indirect path from the text, obtaining information, to reflection, the formation of a worldview. Of course, in English lessons, group and collective forms of work are an integral part that contributes to education. In the process of such activities, students learn to be

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responsible for completing the task, control each other, and provide mutual assistance. Children develop a sense of collectivism [3]. It is pair and group work that helps students actively interact and exchange views on certain situations and concepts, and then form their own point of view.

However, this activity is not limited to just one discussion. The solution that was born during the discussion of any situation is presented to the whole class, and the children choose the best one, clearly arguing their position.

Another effective method of education is game technologies. G.K. Selevko [2] classifies games as follows:

- business;
- organizational and activity;
- role-playing;
- innovative games;
- didactic.

Role-playing games are often used in English lessons, which are also a method of collective interaction. So, role-playing games are an interactive method that provides an opportunity to learn empirically, through a deliberately organized life situation. There are several variations of this technology. For example, a certain model of student behavior can be discussed in advance, or only the result of the interaction is stipulated, and the participant has the opportunity to make a decision independently and be responsible for his choice. In the latter case, the child has the opportunity to improvise.

Role-playing games are both educational and gaming practices. For students, this is creativity, and the educational nature of this activity is not conscious for them. For a teacher, this is a unique opportunity to achieve the goals and objectives set in a foreign language lesson: mastering new lexical units, developing dialogic speech skills, practicing monologues, teaching the rules of etiquette, raising a spiritual, moral and tolerant personality, etc.

There are certain requirements for gaming technologies that must be followed in order to effectively master this technique.

First of all, a role-playing game should be interesting and as close as possible to a real communication situation. Students need to be motivated to successfully complete a creative task.

The teacher must competently organize the game and think over the form and content so that the entire class or group accepts this proposal. It is very important to convey to each participant the rules, the implementation of which teaches them to comprehend an imaginary situation, interact harmoniously with the team and simply enjoy the game, the joy of successfully fulfilling the requirements. Particular attention should be paid to the atmosphere of the game. It should be friendly and creative. The more comfortable the student feels, the more proactive he will be, therefore, in speech communication he will be able to successfully try himself in different social roles: as an adult, take on the duties of a certain family member, a representative of some profession, be a fairy-tale/cartoon character or choose an ethnographic role. From the point of view of mastering the language material, the game should involve all participants and provide a variety of practice of all vocabulary or grammar on a certain topic.

In the lesson, the teacher sets the task not only to teach the child, but also to educate him, therefore many role-playing games are also aimed at the spiritual and moral development of the individual. The plot-role-playing game helps to form the following qualities in the student: responsibility, discipline, readiness to provide help and support to a comrade, the ability to get involved in different types of

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activities, the ability to competently and conflict-free defend their point of view, look at the situation from different angles and make the most optimal decision. Role-playing games perform several functions: educational (development of speech skills), educational (instilling moral qualities in the student), motivating (encourages students to communicate in a foreign language), compensatory (children have the opportunity to realize their need for communication).

G.K. Selevko also provides a classification of games by prevailing (dominant) methods and techniques:

- problematic, search, research;
- creative, heuristic;
- project;
- information, computer, multimedia [2].

Spiritual and moral education is also successfully implemented with the help of project-based gaming technologies.

CONCLUSION

Our research has shown that today's society needs a tolerant personality, who has knowledge of the moral and ethical standards of different cultures and respects the traditions of other people. A foreign language occupies a special place in the process of educating students, because it is not only a school discipline, but also an instrument of international dialogue. Children of all ages love to play and strive for self-expression and individuality. It is gaming technologies that allow us to create a friendly and creative atmosphere in an English lesson and ensure effective assimilation of educational material.

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